

A User Experience Framework for Online Examination Systems in Higher Education

Nonzwelo Makama¹ [0009-0006-0891-1855], Corné J. van Staden² [0000-0002-3991-3128] and Phumza Makgato-Khunou³ [0000-0001-9811-9365]

¹ UNISA, Johannesburg, South Africa

55022146@mylife.unisa.ac.za, vstadcj1@unisa.ac.za,
makgapm@unisa.ac.za

Abstract. The rapid shift to Online Examinations in Higher Education, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, has exposed significant challenges related to system usability, reliability, accessibility, and academic integrity. While online assessment systems are increasingly adopted in Open Distance e-Learning (ODEL) institutions, limited research has focused on systematically integrating user experience (UX) principles into the design and evaluation of OESs. This study addresses this gap by investigating the user experience challenges faced by students and academics in Online Examination environments and proposing a structured UX framework to guide the design of effective and trustworthy OESs. Grounded in Design Science Research (DSR), this study synthesizes theoretical and empirical literature on online assessments, e-learning systems, and UX models to develop an initial conceptual framework. A scoping and integrative literature review was conducted to identify key UX dimensions, socio-technical challenges, and design principles relevant to Online Examinations in Higher Education. The framework integrates usability, engagement, fairness, system reliability, accessibility, and security as core UX constructs, contextualized within the operational realities of an ODeL institution. The proposed framework contributes theoretically by extending UX research into the domain of Online Examinations and practically by offering design guidelines for improving digital assessment platforms. The framework serves as a design artefact for subsequent empirical validation and iterative refinement, with implications for universities seeking to enhance the credibility, effectiveness, and user-centered design of Online Examination systems.

Keywords: Online Examinations, User Experience (UX), e-Assessment, Design Science Research, Higher Education, Open Distance e-Learning (ODEL), UX framework, Online Examination Systems (OESs)

1 Introduction

The implementation of Online Examinations in South African Higher Education has greatly modernized assessment procedures and transformed institutional teaching and learning paradigms. The South African education system includes public and private

institutions governed by the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET). This paper will focus on a particular Public Higher Education Institution (PHEI). For numerous years, PHEI functioned under an Open Distance and Learning (ODL) paradigm, and the institution has subsequently shifted to an Open Distance and e-Learning (ODeL) model as part of its strategic initiative to embrace digital platforms for teaching and Online Examination [40]. In 2022, the institution transitioned from Sakai to Moodle, as part of its strategy transformation to ODeL, utilizing a widely adopted open-source learning platform to resolve scalability, performance, and integration issues linked to legacy system [23, 39].

The COVID-19 pandemic strengthened this digital transformation, compelling universities to transition from traditional venue-based examinations to online assessments [7, 6]. Consequently, PHEI implemented Online Examination platforms during the May/June examination period, signifying a substantial transformation in its evaluation methodology [37]. Online Examinations provide flexibility, accessibility, and efficiency; but they also present considerable issues concerning infrastructure, system reliability, academic integrity, and user experience (UX) [26, 31]. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed structural inequalities in digital access, predominantly in developing contexts where students had connectivity challenges and restricted availability of digital devices [40, 4]. The rapid transition to online learning and assessment exposed systemic vulnerabilities in institutional infrastructure and highlighted the critical role of essential importance of robust digital platforms for maintaining academic continuity.

The progression of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) has expedited digital transformation in Higher Education, enabling blended and fully online learning models [28]. Learning Management Systems such as Moodle, Open edX, and NEO LMS play a significant role in course delivery, Online Examination, and academic administration [22, 3].

Online Examinations, defined as web-based assessment platforms supporting remote participation through digital devices [20], became an essential component of e-learning environments. However, concerns regarding examination integrity, fairness, system reliability, and usability have been widely reported [15, 31]. Evidence suggests that Online Examinations may enhance prospects for academic dishonesty, with a considerable percentage of students viewing online assessments as more susceptible to manipulation [15, 1].

At PHEI, the Online Examination system has been criticized regarding system performance, assessment credibility, and reliability [10, 24]. Technical problems, such as network outages, system capacity constraints and invigilation inefficiencies, further undermined user confidence and institutional credibility [37]. The challenges highlight the necessity for methodical strategy in the design of OESs that emphasizes usability, reliability, fairness and security. Despite the integration of Online Examinations into digital education, numerous institutions lack systematic frameworks for the design and evaluation of user experience in online assessment systems. User Experience (UX) is characterized as the users' perceptions and reactions arising from the utilization of a system, service, or product within a certain context [17]. Bad UX can cause frustration, disconnection, and a lack of confidence in the system [36, 16]. This paper addresses the lack of a structured UX framework for OESs within an ODeL context. In the absence

of such a framework, essential elements affecting system usability, accessibility, reliability, student involvement, Online Examination integrity, and security concerns remain inadequately addressed. This paper develops a theory-informed conceptual UX framework for OES to support their efficient design, evaluation and implementation in Higher Education. Future phases of the PhD research will concentrate on gathering empirical data to evaluate, validate, and refine the framework. Consequently, this paper examines the following research question: What key elements and design features should be included in a user experience framework for OESs?

The study follows the DSR methodology proposed by [30]. This paper discusses step 3 of DSR process: Design and Development, during which a conceptual framework artifact is created. The suggested UX framework is developed through literature synthesis and theoretical modeling, functioning as a preliminary artifact for evaluation and refinement in subsequent DSR processes.

This study conceptually contributes by developing a conceptual UX framework for OESs, synthesized from relevant theories and literature on UX, Online Examination and technology adoption. The framework incorporates key UX dimensions, including usability, fairness, trust, and system reliability within the context of Online Examinations. Practically, the research provides design oriented assistance based on the conceptual framework, offering principles and recommendations to inform the design and enhancement of OESs, predominantly in PHEI and analogous Higher Education contexts. Methodologically, the study adopts a DSR approach illustrating how theory informed literature synthesis can facilitate development that can then be evaluated and refined in ODeL context.

2 Literature review

2.1 Related work

Over the past few years, the landscape of Higher Education (HE) has been revolutionized, marked by rapid growth in enrollment and wider variety of programs and degrees offered by diverse institutions [2]. With Online Examinations becoming a fundamental component in e-learning environments. Examination in online environment are administered through web-based platforms, enabling learners to engage without being physically present in examination room. Online Examinations enable students to complete assessments remotely using digital devices connected to institutional platforms [5]. These systems have benefits including scalability, adaptability, and automated evaluation process; yet, they also present socio-technical difficulties that impact usability, fairness, security, and student engagement [26, 31]. The COVID-19 pandemic expedited the worldwide transition to online examinations, requiring a swift change from conventional venue-based assessments and traditional invigilation to remote digital evaluation [7, 6]. This transition maintained academic continuity but exposed infrastructural limitations and presented issues related to academic integrity, user experience and privacy [1, 27, 29]. In developing contexts, inequities in digital access intensified

challenges related to online exams, especially for students with limited connectivity and device availability [8].

The implementation of OESs in Higher Education has intensified due to the increasing demand for adaptable, technology-facilitated evaluation. Research indicates that these systems encompass more than mere digitalization of conventional examinations; they represent socio-technical setting wherein system design, user interaction, and contextual elements collectively impact academic outcomes and user satisfaction [11, 13]. Recent literature has identified invigilation platforms such as Moodle, Invigilator App, IRIS, and AI-supported proctoring solutions that offer Online Examination monitoring, marking and reporting [18, 29]. Although these tools improve efficiency and uphold academic integrity, challenges such as privacy, data security, technical disruptions and digital divide persist, jeopardizing the credibility, fairness, and legitimacy of Online Examination if left unaddressed [1, 27, 29]. Existing research emphasizes that OESs are not solely technological intricate socio-technical ecosystems in which institutional policies, system design, and user perceptions interact dynamically [11]. Technical disruptions, usability problems with interfaces, and surveillance systems can all significantly affect students' feelings of fairness, trust and emotional wellness [34]. These findings imply that the successful design of an Online Examination should not only focus on technological performance but also overall user experience considerations.

Previous research has highlighted that online evaluation tools differ in function and influence on users. Learning Management Systems (LMS) such as Moodle, Blackboard, and Canvas are an important in the delivery of Online Examination in Higher Education [35]. Advanced platforms such as blockchain-based systems, offer improved security, transparency and proof of completion assessments [13]. Invigilation applications, including webcam-based monitoring to AI-driven behavioral analysis, uphold academic integrity but may heighten stress due to technical ambiguities, surveillance mechanisms and especially if students lack clarity regarding data utilization and privacy measures [34, 29]. These studies suggest that the success of Online Examinations is influenced not only by technological competencies but also by the quality of human-system interaction and confidence in institutional practices.

3 Theoretical Background

3.1 User Experience in digital assessment context

The ISO (2019) definition of UX emphasized that it is shaped by three interrelated components: User, System and Context of Use. Complex or inadequately designed systems can exacerbate **user** anxiety, diminish engagement, and impair academic performance [21, 36]. Conversely, **systems** that are intuitive, transparent, and user-centric can enhance engagement, trust, fairness, and satisfaction [16]. In a digital learning **context**, UX includes practical factors alongside emotional and experiential aspects such as satisfaction, engagement, and emotional comfort [12]. **Context** is crucial as students may complete assessments under diverse home environments, technology limitations, or socio-economic challenges. Therefore, incorporating UX principles into the design and

evaluation of OESs is essential for achieving a balance among academic integrity, usability, accessibility and ethical consideration. Additionally UX is influenced by users' perception of trust and transparency, particularly in an Online Examination context.

3.2 Technology acceptance and adoption theories

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) offer essential theoretical frameworks for comprehending user acceptance of Online Examination systems. TAM suggests that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use influence technology adoption [9]; this explains acceptance of Online Examination based on usability and perceived value. UTAUT extends this by incorporating performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, and social influence [41]; this highlights the role of institutional support, infrastructure and social influence in system adoption. These theories are particularly relevant in Online Examinations, where institutional support, system reliability, and perceived legitimacy affect acceptance and sustained usage.

3.3 Trust, ethics, and fairness in Online Examination

Trust-based models are relevant in the setting of Online Examinations, particularly for institutions utilizing remote proctoring applications. The model emphasizes that the factors contributing to user acceptance in OESs depend on the transparency of technical failures, privacy, and procedural fairness, especially in contexts involving surveillance and automated decision-making [29]. Online proctoring systems have raised ethical concerns related to data privacy, bias, and dishonest accusations of misconduct [38]. These concerns affect students' perceptions of fairness and institutional legitimacy, underscoring the need for ethical-by-design approaches in OESs.

3.4 Engagement and user characteristics in digital environment

The online engagement frameworks identify five critical components that supports effective student engagement in online teaching and learning environments: social, cognitive, emotional, behavioral and collaborative engagement [32]. These elements provide a comprehensive perspective on student involvement which is essential for the success of online educational efforts. User characteristics such as digital literacy, prior experience, and cognitive capabilities, further influence system interaction and performance [19]. These factors highlight the necessity of inclusive and adaptive design systems in diverse Higher Education contexts.

4 Conceptual Framework development

4.1 Core UX dimensions in OESs

The recent study has shown that UX has a substantial impact on students' engagement, performance and acceptability of Online Examinations. In the digital assessment context UX is a multifaceted construct that includes usability, system reliability, trust, fairness, emotional well-being and accessibility [21, 17]. Inadequate usability, complex navigation, or intrusive surveillance can exacerbate cognitive load, increase anxiety, and diminish confidence, even in technically functional systems [14, 16]. Conversely, systems featuring intuitive interfaces, explicit communication, and transparency in proctoring procedures foster engagement, trust, and a sense of fairness [16, 38]. These dimensions demonstrate that UX encompasses not only usability but also psychological, ethical, and socio-technical factors, emphasizing the distinct challenges of high-stakes, remote assessment context.

Table 1. Core UX Dimensions in Online Examination Systems

UX Dimension	Description	Relevance to Online Examinations	Key Sources
Usability & Easy of interaction	Efficient and intuitive interaction with minimal cognitive effort	Poor usability increases errors and anxiety	[21, 17]
Reliability & System Performance	Stability and responsiveness of platforms	Failures undermine fairness and legitimacy	[11, 13]
Trust, Transparency & Academic Integrity	Confidence in ethical and secure operation	Essential in surveillance contexts	[29]
Emotional Experience & Anxiety Management	Stress, fear, and perceived control	Affects performance and engagement	[14, 11]
Accessibility & Inclusivity	Ability for diverse users to participate	Critical in unequal contexts	[8, 33]
Fairness & Perceived Equity	Consistent and unbiased assessment	Influences legitimacy	[16, 38]

4.2 Contextual challenges affecting Online Examination UX

Empirical research identified persistent UX challenges in Online Examinations. Technical failures, including system crashes and connectivity disruptions, intensify anxiety and diminish confidence in the validity of an examination [11, 25]. The implementation of AI-based proctoring raises issues of surveillance and privacy, leading to inquiries about trust and ethical considerations [34, 29]. The discrepancy in infrastructure and access to technology further increases inequalities particularly in developing countries which undermines perceptions of fairness and inclusivity [8]. Furthermore, inadequate

user readiness, ambiguous instructions, and inconsistent institutional support adversely impact the UX for both students and academic staff [14, 11]. These challenges collectively illustrate that the UX of Online Examinations arises from complex interactions among technology, policy, institutional practices and user characteristics.

Table 2. Contextual Challenges affecting Online Examination UX

Challenge	Description	Impact on UX	Supporting Literature
Technical Failures & Connectivity Instability	System crashes and latency	Anxiety, distrust	[11, 25]
Elevated Emotional Stress	Fear of disruption and unfamiliarity	Reduced engagement	[14, 11]
Surveillance & Privacy Concerns	Proctoring and data monitoring	Trust erosion	[34, 29]
Infrastructural Inequities	Device and bandwidth disparities	Perceived unfairness	[8]

4.3 Theoretical integration and framework structure

This study formulates a conceptual foundation by synthesizing Hassenzahl’s UX models, ISO human-centered design principles, the TAM model, the ATAUT model, trust-based UX models, engagement frameworks and theories of user characteristics. These theories guide the interpretation of user perceptions, emotional responses, and adoption behaviours in Online Examination settings.

Table 3. Theoretical foundations informing the framework

Theory/Framework	Core focus	Contribution to Online Examination UX
Hassenzahl UX Model	Pragmatic vs hedonic experience	Explains emotional-functional interplay
ISO 9241-210	Human-centred design	Inclusivity and context-of-use
TAM	Usefulness & ease of use	Adoption predictors
UTAUT	Social and infrastructural influences	Institutional readiness
Trust-based UX	Transparency and privacy	Surveillance ethics
Engagement Frameworks	Cognitive, behavioural, emotional engagement	Student interaction during exams
User Characteristics Models	Digital literacy, cognition	Adaptive interface design

The proposed initial conceptual framework conceptualizes UX as a three-layered structure:

1. **Core UX dimensions** - representing target experiential qualities.
2. **Contextual challenges** - representing barriers influencing UX outcomes.
3. **Theoretical foundations** - providing interpretive and design lenses.

Fig. 1. Depicts the proposed conceptual framework derived from the literature, integrating core UX dimensions, contextual challenges, and theoretical underpinnings informed by DSR, user experience theory, and existing models of online learning and assessment.

Fig. 1. Initial conceptual framework for user experience in Online Examination systems

The framework conceptualizes UX as a multi-layered construct consisting of (1) core experiential dimensions (usability, reliability, trust, emotional experience, accessibility, and fairness), (2) contextual challenges influencing user perceptions and system outcomes, and (3) theoretical foundations informing design and evaluation. The model emphasizes the dynamic interaction between system design, institutional context, and user perceptions, forming the basis for iterative refinement through Design Science Research

4.4 Conceptual framework contribution

The initial conceptual framework establishes a foundation for designing and developing a framework specifically customized to Online Examination systems in Higher Education. The framework combines pragmatic and hedonic UX elements with contextual challenges and theoretical models, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of UX

in online assessment setting. The developed conceptual framework serves as the foundational artefact for subsequent investigation and iterative refinement. The second phase will be detailed in the research methodology chapter of this study.

4.5 Gap and contributions to knowledge

This study contributes to knowledge in the fields of Online Examinations, user experience, and digital assessment design in several ways. First, it offers a cohesive conception of user experience in OESs by synthesizing usability, emotional experience, trust, accessibility, and fairness into a unified socio-technical framework, there by advancing previous research that has generally examined these dimensions separately. Second, the study presents a preliminary multi-layered conceptual framework that links core UX dimensions, contextual challenges, and theoretical foundations, thereby providing a structured artefact to inform the design and evaluation of OESs in Higher Education. Third, by explicitly incorporating infrastructural inequities, connectivity limitations, surveillance concerns, and assessment-related emotional stress, the study contextualizes UX theory within a developing and inequitable Higher Education setting, addressing a gap identified in the models. Fourth, the research synthesizes established theories including Hassenzahl's UX model, ISO 9241-210 human-centered design principles, TAM, UTAUT, trust-based frameworks, and socio-technical theory into a unified explanatory structure customized for critical digital assessment contexts, in that way progressing theoretical integration across experiential, behavioral, and ethical dimensions. Finally, the proposed framework provides actionable design guidance for institutions and system developers, informing policy, platform design, and implementation strategies, while also serving as a foundational artefact for DSR and subsequent empirical validation and refinement.

4.6 Research design and validation roadmap

In accordance with DSR principles, the proposed conceptual framework the initial artefact of this study, derived from problem identification and literature synthesis. Subsequent research phases will empirically evaluate the framework with students and academics using mixed methods, including surveys, interviews, usability testing, and system performance evaluation. The study will validate, extend, and operationalize the framework constructs in real-world Online Examination contexts through iterative refinement cycles.

5 Discussion

This study synthesizes literature on Online Examinations, user experience, and socio-technical systems to develop an initial conceptual framework for the design and evaluation of Online Examination platforms. The findings emphasize that user experience in Online Examinations extends conventional usability issues to include emotional, ethi-

cal, infrastructural, and fairness-related dimensions. Furthermore, these results correspond with the previous studies indicating that high-stakes digital assessments represent complex socio-technical ecosystems characterized by the dynamic interplay of technological, organizational, and human factors [11, 13].

The proposed framework enhances UX research by integrating pragmatic and hedonic dimensions with contextual challenges and theoretical models. The current UX frameworks predominantly focus report on general software or e-learning contexts; this framework explicitly addresses the distinct challenges of critical assessments, encompassing surveillance, academic integrity, infrastructural inequities, and emotional stress. By contextualizing UX theory within a developing Higher Education environment, this study contributes to the limited body of research addressing digital assessment in unequal and resource-constrained contexts.

6 Conclusion

This paper developed an initial UX conceptual framework for OESs in Higher Education. By synthesizing literature on UX, online assessments, technology acceptance, and socio-technical theory, the study identified core experiential dimensions and contextual challenges shaping digital assessment environments. The proposed framework contributes theoretically by extending UX research into critical assessment contexts and practically by providing design guidance for institutions and system developers. The framework serves as a foundational artefact for design science-driven empirical validation and refinement, supporting the development of trustworthy, fair, and user-centered OESs in diverse Higher Education contexts.

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